

PRODUCTIVE WAYS IN TEACHING PEDAGOGICAL TERMINOLOGY

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Abstract. *The article discusses effective ways to teach pedagogical terms. It also helps students to practice with pedagogical terms, while such activities help them to strengthen their vocabulary and develop their lexical skills.*

Keywords: *pedagogical, terminology, method, interactive, teaching process, foreign language, lexical competence.*

ПРОДУКТИВНЫЕ МЕТОДЫ ОБУЧЕНИЯ ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКОЙ ТЕРМИНОЛОГИИ

Аннотация. *В статье рассматриваются эффективные способы преподавания педагогических терминов. Это также помогает студентам попрактиковаться в педагогических терминах, а такие занятия помогают им укрепить словарный запас и развить лексические навыки.*

Ключевые слова: *педагогический, терминология, метод, интерактив, учебный процесс, иностранный язык, лексическая компетентность.*

Introduction

Teaching students pedagogical terminology in the course of English for Academic Purposes (EAP) has always been a subject of interest for researchers. This interest has been enhanced by the necessity to acquire pedagogical vocabulary for the successful organization of pedagogical activity. Therefore, it is evident that scholars and teachers must find the most effective ways to make students practice pedagogical terminology in EAP classes.

During the selection of an effective method, it became evident that interactive activity can enhance the process of acquiring pedagogical terminology and ensure effective utilizing lexical competence in constructive communication. The following thesis statement can be formulated as the necessity to maintain professional information while listening to or reading academic works, and the need to use pedagogical terms in oral and written communication to urge the students to master the terminology. Thus using an interactive method in the teaching process can promote the process of studying and learning vocabulary and provide students with the knowledge of terms and skills to use pedagogical vocabulary to lexical discourse. Being preoccupied with the task of finding an effective method of teaching pedagogical terms, an idea that interactive teaching can be a proper mechanism for students' vocabulary development, has been put forward. Interaction helps involve students in performing activities with pedagogical terms, and such activities can enhance vocabulary acquisition and promote the development of lexical subskills. Interactive teaching has long been used in the practice of foreign language education, but applying interactive methods of teaching pedagogical terms to the 3rd year students in the specialty of Foreign Language and Literature, is new. A great number of foreign researchers discussed the successful ways of teaching vocabulary (Carter & McCarthy, 1988; Gairns & Stuart, 1989; Lewis, 1997).

But we are interested in the methods and techniques which can be organized under interactive teaching. So we address Arend's experience (2000), which highlights interactive

methods of teaching as presentation, direct instruction, concept teaching, cooperative learning, problem-based instruction, and classroom discussion. Interactive teaching includes role-plays and simulations (Ellis, 2003; Diamond & Gutloyn, 2006; Ellis, 2003; Borshchovetska & Semenchuk, 2009).

Therefore, interactive teaching is an adequate didactic means for the development students' skills of producing and presenting products of their common activity. It also provides comfortable conditions for making projects, conducting educational processes, achieving "high results in the development of professional competence and student's personality" (Chernylevsky, 2002. p. 53).

Modern multimedia also helps to provide interactive cooperation, and constant communication of students and allows the teachers to lead students' work aimed at mastering a foreign language. Besides, through interacting with native-speaking partners through multimedia (chats, emails, etc.), students acquire the experience in cross-cultural competence, which is essential in the modern globalized world. Now we move to the analysis of pedagogical literature in the part of teaching/learning vocabulary. Well-known scholars have paid considerable attention to teaching students different facets of foreign-language terminology. In particular, Berman (1970) indicated close relations between teaching special terminology and teaching students their professional disciplines. He emphasized a wide range of techniques for disclosing the meaning of receptive (passive) vocabulary: (a) translating with a parallel explaining new words and searching for adequate equivalents of such terms in the students' mother tongue; (b) guessing the meaning from the context; (c) revealing the meaning of a word by analyzing its world-building elements, etc. The scientist claims, it is important that learning new vocabulary and fixing it in the student's memory should be not only contextual but must be conducted with the help of sufficient examples which show different collocations of new words and their variety of meanings in different contexts.

To reveal the efficacy of interactive methods for development of vocabulary subskills, in particular, pedagogical terms we undertook the experiment with four groups of the 3-rd year at the EAP classes. The material of the experiment was series of exercises and tasks with the emphasis on interactive performance. The exercises and tasks were worked out on the basis of authentic materials. Based on educators' instructions and good experiences in teaching vocabulary through reading (Gardner, 2004; Diamond & Gutloyn, 2006) we created three groups of interactive activities for pre-reading, while-reading and post-reading stages.

Experimental teaching pedagogical terms within three-stages framework showed good results: the students were active and master pedagogical vocabulary in the context combining various types of interaction for practice. Thus, the interactive methods for teaching pedagogical terms proved their efficacy. Based on the findings, it is possible to conclude that interactive teaching techniques help students to gain experience in using pedagogical terminology through context.

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